

Buried grating fabrication process for 7xx nm DFB laser diodes

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Motivation

- Various applications of high-power distributed feedback laser (DFB) in the 780 to 795 nm wavelength range:
 - molecular oxygen spectroscopy (760 nm)
 - atomic clocks (767, 770, 780 nm for potassium D2, D1 lines, rubidium line)
- Two step epitaxy (epi) and shallow etched gratings allows precise control of low grating coupling coefficients ($\kappa = 1 \dots 2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) by the layer thickness
- Grating integration is the most critical DFB fabrication step, which influences the reliability of the whole process
- Ebeam litho preferred for flexible grating definition (period, duty cycle) to allow the fabrication of a broad portfolio of grating stabilized diode lasers

DFB laser design

- Edge emitting ridge waveguide (RW) laser with $\text{Al}_x\text{Ga}_{1-x}\text{As}$ cladding and confinement layers
- Buried second order gratings ($m = 2$) with
 - 60 nm wide and 13 nm thick GaAsP lines
 - periods $\Lambda = 230 \dots 245 \text{ nm}$ ($\lambda_{\text{DFB}} = 2 n_{\text{eff}} \Lambda / m$)

Analysed process flow

- Standard so far: maN2401 resist followed by three-step wet-etch and NMP
 - shallow isotropic etch is critical to control the grating line dimensions
 - maN removal with NMP leads to impure overgrowth interfaces
- Novel process: HSQ (EM resist LTD), BCl_3/Ar etch and HF cleaning shows excellent overgrowth results, but HSQ dose is ~ 5 times the dose of maN
- Full 3 inch tests exposures with Raith EBPG5200 and VISTEC SB251
 - Layout with 3300 DFB lasers (each laser with $1480 \times 70 \mu\text{m}^2$ grating area)
 - Writing time after Ebeam/DataPrep optimization < 12 hours

SEM on a FIB-cut in the center of the 2.2 μm wide RW

Results and Summary

- Measurements on DFB lasers from the novel process (coated facets with $R_{\text{front}} = 0\%$ and $R_{\text{back}} = 95\%$, p-side up on C-mount)
 - $P_{\text{out}} = 80 \text{ mW}$ at 200 mA, excellent uniformity of the OE-performance of DFB lasers from different parts of the wafer
 - Single-mode, mode-hop free emission with a side-mode suppression $> 50 \text{ dB}$
 - Lifetime tests on 20 lasers at 80 mW ($\sim 200 \text{ mA}$) > 2000 hours without change of optical output power and spectra

Optical spectra and PI-characteristics of a DFB from the novel process (left); DFB mounted on C-Mount (right)

Lifetime tests of 20 DFB lasers at 80 mW cleaved from different parts of the wafer

We present a novel grating fabrication process for 7xx nm DFB laser diodes. We demonstrate that HSQ ebeam resist in combination with a shallow dry-etch and HF cleaning results in excellent DFB device performances for a large number of devices. The developed, simplified HSQ process can also be applied for (i) the fabrication of DFB laser diodes emitting at different wavelengths (e.g. 1064 nm) and (ii) for other InP patterns buried in $\text{Al}_x\text{Ga}_{1-x}\text{As}$ (e.g. 2D gratings for PCSEL).